

Synthesis of 5-Diethylaminomethyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles—their Fungitoxicity, Antispasmodic and Antihistaminic Activities

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5-Diethylaminomethyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles and 5-diethylaminomethyl-4-phenyl/methyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles/imidazoles were prepared by interaction of 2-substituted-aminothiazoles/imidazoles with diethylamine and *p*-formaldehyde. All these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against the pathogen *Carvularia lunata*. Antispasmodic and antihistaminic activity of some of these compounds were studied by using isolated strips of guineapig intestine.

THIS is in continuation to our earlier work¹ on synthesis, fungicidal and pharmacological studies of some new thiazole derivatives. Thiazoles possess significant antifungal²⁻⁵, antihistaminic⁶ and antispasmodic⁷ activities. Encouraged by the results of our earlier work on 2-substituted-aminothiazoles, some 5-diethylaminomethyl-2-substituted-thiazoles/imidazoles were synthesised and their fungicidal and pharmacological activities were studied. 5-Diethylaminomethyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles (1a-j) were prepared by the condensation of 2-substituted-aminothiazoles with diethylamine and *p*-formaldehyde. Further, 5-diethylaminomethyl-4-phenyl/methyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles/imidazoles (2a-e) were synthesised by the interaction of 4-phenyl/methyl-2-substituted-aminothiazoles/imidazoles with diethyl amine and *p*-formaldehyde.

stretching vibration. The characteristic peaks of thiazole nucleus are noticed at 1470 cm⁻¹ (strong-ring C=N) and 1250 cm⁻¹ (strong-ring C-N). Nmr spectra are seen to be similar for 1a and 2a. Sidechain -CH₂ protons gave signal at δ 2.18. A multiple peak at δ 7.8 is typical of thiazole and aromatic protons. Sharp singlet noticed at δ 5.2 is by the NH protons. The mass spectrum of 1a gave the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 261. Other major peaks were noticed at *m/z* 189, 150, 92, 77, 72, 58 and 39 from which the fragmentation of the molecule can be built up as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Structure of all the synthesised compounds were established from their elemental analysis, ir, nmr and mass spectral studies. Strong absorption occurs at 1350 cm⁻¹ in 1a and 2a due to tertiary N-C

The molecular ion peak of 2a appeared at *m/z* 348. From the peaks at *m/z* 233, 175, 115, 102, 77,

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73, 72, 58 and 25, the fragmentation of the molecule is framed as in Scheme 2.

All the prepared compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against the pathogen *Carvularia lunata* by using spore germination tests⁸ at various concentrations. In general, the compounds **1** (Table 1) showed appreciable fungitoxicity against the test pathogen. Among them, **1b**, **1d** and **1e** were most active and inhibit spore germination above 95% at 1 000 ppm concentration. When R is C₆H₄Cl (*m*-), the fungicidal activity was maximum (100%). Except **2d** (Table 1), the others have not shown encouraging fungicidal activity. When compared to our earlier work¹, it is seen that no additional toxicity is brought by introducing diethylaminomethyl group to the thiazole moiety.

Compounds **1a-g** and **2a-e** were screened for their antihistaminic and antispasmodic activities by mounting strips of guineapig intestine on Dale's isolated organ bath and following our earlier procedure¹. It may be seen from Table 1 that compounds **1b**, **1c**, **1f**, **1g**, **2a**, **2d** and **2e** have shown considerable antihistaminic activity. Further, **1c**, **1f**, **2a** and **2d** have exhibited significant antispasmodic activity. The activities of the tested compounds are comparable to the standard drug antazoline hydrochloride. Acute and chronic toxicity of these active compounds are under investigation. In comparison to our earlier observation¹, it may be pointed out that the pharmacological activity is considerably improved by introducing diethylaminomethyl group in the thiazole nucleus.

Experimental

5-Diethylaminomethyl-2-phenylaminothiazole (1a) : 2-Phenylaminothiazole was prepared by following the procedure described earlier¹. Diethylamine (0.8 g), paraformaldehyde (2.5 g) and 2-phenylaminothiazole (1.76 g) were taken in glacial acetic acid (10 ml). The resulting mixture was refluxed for 10 h on a water-bath. It was then allowed to cool to room temperature and 5% potassium carbonate solution (20 ml) was added till the mixture became alkaline. The resulting light red compound was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol to yield light red crystals, (75%), m.p. 116°.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, M.p. AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	S% : Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Fungicidal activity against <i>C. lunata</i> % inhibition at 1 000 ppm	Guineapig intestine	
						Antihistaminic activity	Antispasmodic activity
						MED-50 μg	MED-50 μg
1a	H	C ₆ H ₅	12.15 (12.31)	116	90	No action	No action
1b	H	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>p</i> -)	11.47 (11.68)	186	95	80	No action
1c	H	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i> -)	10.75 (10.86)	114	85	80	80
1d	H	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>m</i> -)	10.54 (10.86)	126	100	No action	No action

(Table 1 contd.)

1e	H	C ₆ H ₄ COOH(o-)	10.45 (10.58)	103	95	No action	No action
1f	H	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p-)	10.24 (10.49)	250	85	160	80
1g	H	C ₁₀ H ₇ (←-)	10.16 (10.32)	250	70	80	No action
1h	H	C ₁₀ H ₇ (β-)	10.27 (10.32)	108	68	×	×
1i	H	C ₈ H ₈ N	12.19 (12.24)	250	70	×	×
1j	H	C ₈ H ₈ NCH ₃ (p-)	11.52 (11.64)	250	90	×	×
2a	C ₆ H ₅	Benzothiazolyl	16.16 (16.24)	159	70	80	80
2b	OH ₂	Benzothiazolyl	18.98 (19.27)	192	80	No action	No action
2c	OH ₂	Benzoimidazolyl	9.87 (10.02)	208	65	No action	No action
2d	C ₆ H ₅	Benzoimidazolyl	8.35 (8.49)	250	95	80	80
2e	C ₆ H ₅	Quinonyl	8.88 (8.24)	127	75	160	No action

5-Diethylaminomethyl-4-phenyl-2-benzothiazolyl-aminothiazole (2a) : 4-Phenyl-2-benzothiazolylaminothiazole was prepared by the procedure reported earlier¹. Adopting the procedure similar to 1a, 2a was synthesised by taking 4-phenyl-2-benzothiazolyl-aminothiazole (3 g), p-formaldehyde (2.5 g) and diethylamine (0.8 g) in acetic acid (15 ml), (70%), m.p. 159°.

The relevant data on elemental analysis, fungicidal, antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities of the compounds are enlisted in Table 1.

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